

G-PLANET-X P&L Summary

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Project Objectives

This Capstone Project marks the final requirement (Course 9 of 9) in the **HarvardX Data Science Professional Certificate** program, delivered and supervised by Dr. Rafael Irizarry of the Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health.

The purpose of this project is to build a reproducible data pipeline in R that analyzes program offerings and enrollment data across Ontario's community colleges, with a focus on disciplines related to Artificial Intelligence (AI).

This project serves as a **foundational input** into the submitter's Global Doctor of Business Administration (GDBA) dissertation at the **Swiss School of Business and Management (SSBM)**, which investigates **AI Readiness in Ontario's Community Colleges** in the context of the Fourth Industrial Revolution.

Specifically, the outputs from this R project feed into the **P (Programs)** and **L (Learners)** attributes of the **G-PLANET-X** framework, a composite scoring model used to quantify and compare AI integration across post-secondary institutions.

This project draws on open data available to the public by the **Ministry of Colleges and Universities** of the Government of Ontario.

Disclaimer 1:

The Ontario Open Data site does not allow for the automatic download of the dataset.

The data is published only in Excel spreadsheet format and requires **manual download** prior to running this R script. URL: [Ontario College Enrolment Data (2023–2024) (<https://data.ontario.ca/dataset/e9634682-b9dc-46a6-99b4-e17c86e00190>)]

Disclaimer 2:

Collège Boréal did not report enrollment data for AI-related courses in the 2023–2024 dataset.

The college has submitted enrollment figures for other disciplines this year and had reported AI programs in previous years.

The omission is presumed to be a reporting gap, not an absence of programming.

```
# GPLANET_P_L_Capstone.R
# Purpose: Evaluate AI Readiness using P (Programs) and L (Learners) metrics
# across Ontario Colleges (2023-2024)

# --- Auto-Install and Load Required Packages ---
install_and_load <- function(pkg) {
  if (!requireNamespace(pkg, quietly = TRUE)) {
    install.packages(pkg, dependencies = TRUE)
  }
}
```

```
library(pkg, character.only = TRUE)
}
```

```
install_and_load("readxl")
install_and_load("dplyr")
```

```
##
## Attaching package: 'dplyr'

## The following objects are masked from 'package:stats':
##
##   filter, lag

## The following objects are masked from 'package:base':
##
##   intersect, setdiff, setequal, union
```

```
install_and_load("ggplot2")
install_and_load("tidyr")
```

```
options(dplyr.print_max = Inf)
```

```
# --- Set Working Directory ---
```

```
setwd("C:/Projects/HarvardX Capstone/HarvardX")
file_path <- "college_enrolment_headcount_2023-24.xlsx"
```

```
# --- Load 2023-2024 CIP Data ---
```

```
cip_data <- read_excel(file_path, sheet = "CIP") %>%
  filter(`Fiscal Year` == "2023-2024")
```

```
cip_data$`Headcount Full-Time Fall` <- as.numeric(cip_data$`Headcount Full-Time Fall`)
```

```
## Warning: NAs introduced by coercion
```

```
# --- AI-Relevant CIP Codes ---
```

```
ai_cips <- c(
  "10.0304", "11.0101", "11.0102", "11.0103", "11.0104", "11.0199",
  "11.0201", "11.0202", "11.0301", "11.0501", "11.0701", "11.0801",
  "11.0802", "11.0804", "11.0899", "11.0901", "11.1001", "11.1002",
  "11.1003", "11.1006", "11.1099", "11.9999", "15.0305", "15.0405",
  "15.0406", "15.1201", "15.1202", "15.1204", "15.1299", "30.1601",
  "45.0102", "47.0104", "47.0614", "48.0510", "51.2706", "52.0302",
  "52.1201", "52.1206", "52.1299"
)
```

```
# --- Page Break for PDF ---
```

```
cat('\n\\newpage\n')
```

```
## \newpage
```

Table 1: Appendix A: AI-Relevant CIP Codes and Their Titles

CIP.Code	Title
10.0304	Animation, interactive technology, video graphics and special effects
11.0101	Computer and information sciences, general
11.0102	Artificial intelligence
11.0103	Information technology
11.0104	Informatics
11.0199	Computer and information sciences and support services, general, other
11.0201	Computer programming/programmer, general
11.0202	Computer programming, specific applications
11.0301	Data processing and data processing technology/technician
11.0501	Computer systems analysis/analyst
11.0701	Computer science
11.0801	Web page, digital/multimedia and information resources design
11.0802	Data modelling/warehousing and database administration
11.0804	Modelling, virtual environments and simulation
11.0899	Computer software and media applications, other
11.0901	Computer systems networking and telecommunications, general
11.1001	Network and system administration/administrator
11.1002	System, networking and LAN/WAN management/manager
11.1003	Computer and information systems security/auditing/information assurance
11.1006	Computer support specialist
11.1099	Computer/information technology administration and management, other
11.9999	Computer and information sciences and support services, other
15.0305	Telecommunications technology/technician
15.0405	Robotics technology/technician
15.0406	Automation engineer technology/technician
15.1201	Computer engineering technology/technician, general
15.1202	Computer/computer systems technology/technician
15.1204	Computer software technology/technician
15.1299	Computer engineering technologies/technicians, other
30.1601	Accounting and computer science
45.0102	Research methodology and quantitative methods
47.0104	Computer installation and repair technology/technician
47.0614	Alternative fuel vehicle technology/technician
48.0510	CNC machinist technology/CNC machinist
51.2706	Medical informatics
52.0302	Accounting technology/technician and bookkeeping
52.1201	Management information systems, general
52.1206	Information resources management
52.1299	Management information systems and services, other

AI vs. Total Programs by College (2023–2024) (Sorted by % of AI programs)

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AI vs.Total Enrollment by College (2023–2024)

(Sorted by % of AI learners)

